

Suicidal Deaths by Hanging & Poisoning in a Tertiary Care Setting

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ABSTRACT

Background: Suicide is a major public health concern, with hanging and poisoning being the leading methods in South Asia. Understanding demographic patterns and method-specific trends is crucial for targeted prevention. **Objective:** To assess the frequency, demographic characteristics, and method-specific patterns of suicide deaths in a tertiary care setting in Bangladesh. **Methods & Materials:** A cross-sectional study was conducted at Dhaka Medical College Hospital from April 2019 to February 2020, including 115 confirmed suicide deaths. Data on age, gender, marital status, residence, and suicide methods (hanging, poisoning, fall, burns) were collected from hospital records and autopsy reports. Poisoning cases were further categorized by substance type. Associations between suicide methods and demographic factors were analyzed using Pearson Chi-square or Fisher's Exact tests, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant. **Results:** Suicide deaths were most common among individuals aged 31–50 years (34.8%), with females accounting for 58.3% of cases. Married individuals comprised 53.9%, and 61.7% were from rural areas. Hanging (49.6%) and poisoning (39.1%) were the predominant methods, with organophosphorus compounds (64.4%) and aluminium phosphide (31.1%) most frequently used in poisoning cases. Younger individuals (<30 years) were more likely to die by poisoning, while hanging predominated in older adults ($p = 0.028$). Rural residence was significantly associated with hanging, and urban residence with poisoning ($p = 0.04$). No significant associations were observed with gender or marital status. **Conclusion:** Hanging and poisoning are the main suicide methods in this tertiary care setting, influenced by age and residence.

Preventive strategies, including restriction of toxic substances and targeted mental health interventions, are essential to reduce suicide mortality.

Keywords: Suicide, Hanging, Poisoning, Suicide Methods, Demographics, Bangladesh, Tertiary Care.

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INTRODUCTION

Suicide ranks as a major cause of unnatural death globally and demands immediate public health focus to lower mortality rates. Risk factors differ according to age, gender, mental health condition, ethnicity, and various personal traits [1]. It results in 800,000 to 1 million fatalities annually, positioning it 10th worldwide, with a 60% increase in rates over the past 50 years. Sixty percent of cases are attributed to Asia, which includes China, India, and Japan [2]. Research indicates that suicide attempts are frequently associated with mental health conditions like depression, psychiatric disorders, hopelessness, impulsivity, and substance use. Although substance abuse is closely linked to suicidal thoughts, it is a less reliable indicator of actual suicide attempts in individuals experiencing those thoughts [3].

Hanging is a prevalent suicide method globally and has been extensively employed since the medieval era, historically representing roughly half of all suicides [4]. Poisoning from substances like drugs, chemicals, or toxins poses a significant public health issue, particularly in low- and middle-income nations [5]. WHO data indicates that hanging is the most prevalent method of suicide worldwide, while

poisoning is frequent in certain regions of Asia and Latin America due to accessibility and cultural influences [6]. A systematic review of studies from South Asia (2001–2020) that included Bangladesh, India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, and Nepal identified hanging (55.8%) and poisoning (35.3%) as the two most prevalent methods of suicide in the region [7]. Meta-analytic evidence shows hanging is far more lethal than poisoning, partly explaining its higher rate of completed suicides worldwide [8]. A study revealed that self-poisoning with pesticides is a significant factor in suicides globally, particularly in the Western Pacific, where toxic agricultural chemicals are readily available [9].

A content analysis of newspaper reports on suicidal behaviors in Bangladesh found that hanging was the predominant method, followed by poisoning, with several cases linked to familial and social pressures [10]. While hanging and poisoning remain the leading methods of suicide in Bangladesh, existing studies often rely on retrospective hospital records or media reports, providing limited insight into current trends, demographic patterns, and poisoning subtypes in tertiary care settings. This study aims to evaluate suicidal fatalities from hanging, poisoning, and other methods in a

tertiary care hospital, examining their frequency, demographic characteristics, and type of poisoning, to provide evidence for targeted prevention strategies.

METHODS & MATERIALS

This cross-sectional study was conducted at Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh, over a 12-month period from April 2019 to February 2020. The study included 115 confirmed cases of suicide deaths reported during this timeframe. Cases with incomplete or ambiguous records were excluded to ensure data quality and accuracy.

Data were collected from hospital records, autopsy reports, and medico-legal documents, focusing on demographic characteristics (age, gender, marital status, and residence) and suicide-related factors, including the method of suicide (hanging, poisoning, fall from height, and burns) and, for poisoning cases, the type of substance involved (organophosphorus compounds, aluminium phosphide, or amphetamines).

Age was categorized into four groups: <18 years, 18–30 years, 31–50 years, and >51 years, while gender was recorded as male or female. Marital status was classified as married, unmarried, or widowed/divorced,

and residence was categorized as urban or rural.

Data were analyzed using frequencies and percentages for descriptive statistics. The association between suicide methods and demographic variables (age, gender, marital status, and residence) was assessed using the Pearson Chi-square test. In cases where the expected cell frequency was less than five, the Fisher Exact test was applied. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

The study adhered to ethical standards of the hospital, ensuring confidentiality and

anonymity, and all analyses were conducted using de-identified data to protect participant privacy.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows that the highest proportion of suicide deaths occurred among individuals aged 31–50 years (40 cases, 34.8%), followed by those aged 18–30 years (36 cases, 31.3%). Individuals older than 51 years accounted for 25 cases (21.7%), while 14 cases (12.2%) were below 18 years of age. In terms of gender distribution, females represented a higher proportion of deaths,

with 67 cases (58.3%), compared to 48 cases (41.7%) among males, indicating a female predominance in the study population. Regarding marital status, more than half of the cases were married (62 cases, 53.9%), followed by unmarried individuals (41 cases, 35.7%), and a smaller proportion were widowed or divorced (12 cases, 10.4%). With respect to residence, the majority of cases originated from rural areas (71 cases, 61.7%), while 44 cases (38.3%) were from urban areas.

Table 1
Distribution of Suicide Deaths by Demographic Characteristics of the Study Population (n=115).

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age	<18 Years	14	12.2
	18–30 Years	36	31.3
	31–50 Years	40	34.8
	>51 Years	25	21.7
Gender	Male	48	41.7
	Female	67	58.3
Marital Status	Married	62	53.9
	Unmarried	41	35.7
	Widowed/Divorced	12	10.4
Residence	Urban	44	38.3
	Rural	71	61.7

Figure 1 Methods of Suicide among the Study Population.

Figure 1 shows, the predominant method of suicide was hanging, with 57 cases (49.6%), while poisoning followed with 45 cases (39.1%). Falls from heights and burns occurred less often, resulting in 10 (8.7%) and 3 (2.6%) fatalities, respectively. In total, hanging and poisoning combined constituted almost 90% of all suicide

fatalities, suggesting that these are the main methods used in this group.

Figure 2 shows in the cases of suicide involving poisoning, organophosphorus compounds (OPC) were the most prevalent, comprising 29 cases (64.4%). Aluminium phosphide was the second most common,

accounting for 14 cases (31.1%), whereas amphetamine was infrequent, resulting in just 2 fatalities (4.4%). This suggests that OPC and aluminium phosphide are the main toxic substances involved in suicides related to poisoning within the study group.

Figure 2 Distribution of Types of Poisoning among Suicide Deaths.

Overall, hanging (49.6%) and poisoning (39.1%) constituted the vast majority of suicide deaths in this tertiary care setting, accounting for nearly 90% of all cases. A statistically significant association was observed between age group and suicide method ($p = 0.028$), with younger

individuals (<30 years) more frequently dying by poisoning, while hanging predominated among individuals aged 31–50 years. Residence was also significantly associated with suicide method ($p = 0.04$), as rural residents more commonly used to hang, whereas poisoning was relatively

more frequent among urban residents. No statistically significant association was found with gender or marital status. *Table II* demonstrates association between suicide method and demographic characteristics.

Table II

Association of Suicide Method with Age, Gender, Marital Status, and Residence ($n = 115$).

Variable	Category	Hanging n (%)	Poisoning n (%)	Fall n (%)	Burns n (%)	p-value
Age	<18 (n=14)	3 (21.4)	8 (57.1)	2 (14.3)	1 (7.1)	0.028*
	18–30 (n=36)	14 (38.9)	17 (47.2)	3 (8.3)	2 (5.6)	
	31–50 (n=40)	26 (65.0)	10 (25.0)	3 (7.5)	1 (2.5)	
	>51 (n=25)	14 (56.0)	10 (40.0)	2 (8.0)	0 (0.0)	
	Male (n=48)	28 (58.3)	15 (31.3)	4 (8.3)	1 (2.1)	
Female (n=67)	29 (43.3)	30 (44.8)	6 (9.0)	2 (3.0)		
Marital Status	Married (n=62)	35 (56.5)	21 (33.9)	5 (8.1)	1 (1.6)	0.51
	Unmarried (n=41)	17 (41.5)	19 (46.3)	3 (7.3)	2 (4.9)	
	Widowed/Divorced (n=12)	5 (41.7)	5 (41.7)	2 (16.6)	0 (0.0)	
Residence	Urban (n=44)	18 (40.9)	20 (45.5)	4 (9.1)	2 (4.5)	0.04*
	Rural (n=71)	39 (54.9)	25 (35.2)	6 (8.5)	1 (1.4)	

Chi square test/ Fisher Exact test applied; *Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$

DISCUSSION

This study evaluated 115 suicide deaths at a tertiary care hospital in Bangladesh, focusing on the demographic characteristics and methods of suicide. The predominant methods were hanging (49.6%) and poisoning (39.1%), collectively accounting for nearly 90% of cases. Falls from heights and burns were relatively uncommon. Among poisoning cases, organophosphorus compounds (OPC) and aluminium phosphide were the most frequent toxic agents, reflecting the accessibility of agricultural chemicals in Bangladesh, consistent with previous findings on pesticide-related suicides in low- and middle-income countries [11]. A significant association between age and suicide method was observed ($p = 0.028$).

Younger individuals (<30 years) were more likely to die by poisoning, whereas hanging predominated among those aged 31–50 years. This aligns with prior research indicating that younger populations often choose methods that are more readily available, such as poisoning, while older individuals tend to use more lethal methods like hanging [12–14].

Although no statistically significant association was found between gender and suicide method ($p = 0.09$), females accounted for a higher proportion of overall deaths (58.3%). This is consistent with findings from Miranda-Mendizabal et al., which reported gender differences in suicidal behavior, with females more likely to attempt suicide but males more often

completing it through more lethal methods [15]. Similarly, Wu et al. demonstrated that age- and sex-specific suicide mortality varies by method globally, highlighting cultural and socioeconomic influences [12]. Marital status did not show a significant association with suicide method ($p = 0.51$). However, rural residents were significantly more likely to use hanging, while urban residents tended to die more frequently from poisoning ($p = 0.04$). This rural–urban disparity mirrors prior research indicating that geographic location affects both the accessibility of means and the choice of suicide method [16–18]. The dominance of hanging and poisoning, particularly pesticide-related deaths, underscores the urgent need for targeted prevention strategies. Restricting access to

lethal means, such as highly toxic pesticides, along with community-based mental health interventions, may substantially reduce suicide mortality^[11,13]. Additionally, the higher prevalence of suicide among females and young adults highlights the necessity for tailored mental health programs and awareness campaigns focused on these vulnerable groups^[14,15,19]. Consistent with other studies from Bangladesh and South Asia, hanging emerged as the leading suicide method, followed by poisoning^[17, 19]. The demographic patterns observed in this study, including higher suicide rates in females and younger individuals, corroborate findings from national hospital-based analyses^[17,18]. The predominance of rural cases further supports the evidence of geographic disparities in suicide mortality, likely driven by accessibility to lethal methods and sociocultural stressors^[16].

CONCLUSION

The study highlights the critical role of demographic and geographic factors in suicidal deaths in Bangladesh, with hanging and poisoning remaining the most prevalent methods. These findings reinforce the need for age-, gender-, and residence-specific prevention strategies and stricter regulation of toxic substances to reduce the national suicide burden.

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